

A NOTE ON PARACHOR OF SULPHUR AND SOME ORGANIC COMPOUNDS IN SOLUTION

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Sugden (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 128, 32, 1177; 1925, 1525, 1868) has determined the parachor of sulphur in fused state over a wide range of temperature extending from 116° to 445°. The value comes out to be about 49 and is practically constant over the whole range. We have determined the parachor of sulphur in dissolved state using carbon disulphide as the solvent. The results are summarised below.

TABLE I

x (Sulphur).	d .	r .	P_m .	P_x .
0.2179	1.325	35.61	122.9	42.7
0.1967	1.292	33.27	125.6	41.0
0.2315	1.316	33.95	120.7	51.8
0.3359	1.345	32.80	119.0	44.1

Sugden (*loc. cit.*) grouped associated liquids, whose parachor is a function of temperature, into two classes, non-conductors and conductors. Sulphur comes in non-conducting group, hence the deviation from the predicted value could be accounted for by the structure of the complex molecules. The vapour of sulphur polymer near the boiling point chiefly consists of S_8 molecules, while its molecular weight in various solvents indicates a complexity varying from S_6 to S_8 . The Ramsay-Shield constant gives the value S_6 , while Walden constant at boiling point gives a complexity $S_{5.2}$.

In spite of the complexity of the sulphur molecule the value calculated 49 is constant and is not a function of temperature and is of the same order as found from its organic compounds. The value 44 (average), found by us, is of the same order and confirms the statement made by us in various papers that parachor of a solid in dissolved state is generally lower than in liquid or fused state.

The behaviour of sulphur in giving a value of 49 for S atom is explained on the basis of the duplet linkages between sulphur atoms. If, for example, it is supposed that six-membered ring is formed, as in formula S_6 , then the parachor per sulphur atom calculated for this structure is $(6 \times 48.2 - 6.1)/6 = 49.2$ which is very close to the observed value.

The parachor of nitro compounds is of interest. It has been shown that nitro group can be represented in various ways as :

the values for parachor of these groups representations being 98.9, 74.1 and 69.2 res-

pectively. The value as obtained for the liquid in pure state corresponds to 74.1 showing that one of the bond is a semipolar bond. We have tried to determine the value of this group in dissolved state by dissolving *p*-nitrotoluene and 1:3-dinitrobenzene in benzene. The results are recorded below.

TABLE II

Parachor of p-nitrotoluene.

n_D (<i>p</i> -Nitrotoluene).	Temp.	d_4	r .	P_m .	P_x .
0.1647	20.5°	0.9335	29.65	219.5	300.4
0.2676	21.8°	0.9404	35.31	230.1	300.4
"	25.0°	0.9395	35.02	229.6	298.6
"	30.0°	0.9353	34.68	229.9	299.7
0.1903	21.9°	0.9401	30.25	222.8	301.6
"	25.0°	0.9381	30.06	222.9	302.1
"	30.0°	0.9362	29.04	223.1	303.4

TABLE III

Parachor of 1:3-dinitrobenzene.

n_D 1:3-Dinitrobenzene).	Temp.	d_4	r .	P_m .	P_x .
0.1148	23.4°	0.9595	30.70	217.9	315.3
"	25.0°	0.9576	29.68	215.3	307.5
"	30.0°	0.9561	29.32	215.3	307.5
0.06281	23.0°	0.9223	29.57	211.3	316.2
"	25.0°	0.9181	28.97	211.3	316.2
"	30.0°	0.9166	28.91	211.4	318.4
0.09809	22.0°	0.9473	30.14	214.9	313.7
"	25.0°	0.9462	29.35	214.5	313.0
"	30.0°	0.9456	29.35	214.9	313.7

Following table gives the value of nitro group as obtained in solution.

TABLE IV

	<i>p</i> -Nitrotoluene.	1:3-Dinitrobenzene.
Parachor (obs.)	301.1	315.0
P. calc. (omitting nitro group)	299.0	172.9
P for nitro group	72.0	2 * 71.0

"The results indicate that the solution method can give correct values for nitro group as obtained from pure liquid nitro compounds. It is to be seen that the value obtained is low as is expected in accordance with our general observation that parachor values of solids as obtained in dissolved state are some what low.